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**MAMLAKATIMIZDA BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK
INVESTITSİYALARINING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI**
**PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF BUSINESS AND
ENTREPRENEURIAL INVESTMENT IN OUR COUNTRY**
**ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ БИЗНЕСА И
ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКИХ ИНВЕСТИЦИЙ В НАШЕЙ
СТРАНЕ**
ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada biz O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikka investitsiyalarning barqaror yo'nalishini belgilaymiz va amalga oshiramiz.

ANNOTATION

In this article, we will establish and implement a sustainable direction of investing in small business and private entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье изучено приоритетное направление инвестирования в малый бизнес и частное предпринимательство в Республике Узбекистан и изучены пути его реализации, а также улучшение экономических связей с зарубежными странами.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

Moliyaviy faoliyat, foyda, foyda, kredit, resurslar, kapital, bozor iqtisodiyoti

KEYWORDS

Financial activity, profit, profit, credit, resources, capital, market economy

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

Финансовая деятельность, прибыль, прибыль, кредит, ресурсы, капитал, рыночная экономика

INTRODUCTION

Investment (Latin: *investio* — "wrapping") is a long-term investment of capital in different industries, socio-economic programs, innovation, business projects in one's country or abroad for the purpose of economic development. According to the theory of the time value of money, investment is putting funds in order to get benefits in the future. Investment means to commit or reserve capital for a certain period of time. The main purpose of this is to maintain the capital value or, if not, to increase the capital value over time. In terms of economic content, investment reflects tangible and intangible assets mobilized for various activities and the rights to them. Investments include money, securities (shares, bonds, certificates, promissory notes), assets such as land, buildings, structures, intellectual property scientific discoveries, inventions, etc. is used. Investors can be the state, company, enterprise, foreign citizens, residents and others.

MAIN PART

Owners of independent economic property were formed by establishing small business enterprises in Uzbekistan. Small business enterprises are of priority due to their ability to adapt to various macroeconomic conditions and requirements specific to the market economy. The development of small business and private entrepreneurship in various sectors of the economy is one of the important macroeconomic factors of ensuring the stability of our national economy. As a result of the rapid development of small businesses in recent years, it can be explained by the fact that their share in the weight of the gross domestic product created in the country is increasing. Small business is a sector of the economy that adapts to almost all changes in the investment environment. In order to determine the level of attractiveness of the investment environment from the point of view of small business, factors indicating the economic situation in the entire country and regions, the extent to which investments in this branch of the economy are provided with laws and infrastructures, the level of development of the market infrastructure

in the region, and the availability of skilled labor are also and whether or not there are risks associated with other factors is extremely important. At the present time, the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship in our country is significantly influenced by the organization of infrastructure institutions serving it and the improvement of the level of service quality. As a result of this, the results of small business and private entrepreneurship as an important factor in creating new jobs in our country, increasing the income and well-being of the population are becoming significant. The main feature of private entrepreneurship is that, as a rule, regional factors dominate the process of investment attraction. It is necessary to show the need to carry out the analysis of the investment environment by sectors. Because positive investment factors have specific aspects for different industries. In some cases, the factors that can play a positive role in one network are negative for another network, or if any indicator is strong enough for a particular network, this indicator itself is a factor in another network. may be completely lacking for successful development.

The investment environment for small businesses in Uzbekistan is of particular interest. Some indicators specific to small businesses include:

- the regional indicator of the development of the state support system and infrastructure of small business;
- the presence and level of development of large companies competing in the market sectors they occupy (for example, in the service or trade sector);
- level of development of the local banking system and other factors.

Due to their specific characteristics, small enterprises can use only some of the numerous sources that serve to attract investment resources. For example, it should be noted that the sources of internal financing in small businesses do not provide opportunities for self-investment of entrepreneurs at the level of opportunities of large companies. Nevertheless, the use of these resources in small business is able to bring

significant results and has several advantages in terms of engagement efficiency. Thus, increasing the number of convenient sources of investment resources and increasing the efficiency of using existing resources remains an important task of state support structures for small businesses.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, since 1996, the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has established a State Investment Program, which consists of capital investment limits, foreign investments and government-guaranteed loans, as well as a program of constructions at the expense of direct foreign investment and loans. accepts the program. State budget funds, foreign investments, own funds of enterprises and population savings participate in making investments in the republic's economy. In the republic, a network of privatization investment funds (XIF) and companies that implement collective investment of the population in securities has developed.

To provide an accurate and relevant response about the priority directions of business and entrepreneurial investment in your country, I need some additional information:

Country Identification: Could you please specify which country you are referring to? Business and investment landscapes can vary significantly from one country to another.

Current Economic Climate: Understanding the current economic situation in your country, including growth sectors, regulatory changes, and market trends, is crucial.

Government Policies and Incentives: Information about government initiatives, incentives for foreign and domestic investment, and areas targeted for development can help identify priority sectors.

Technological Advancements: Knowing the level of technological adoption and focus areas in technology can point to promising sectors for investment.

Demographic and Social Trends: Demographics (like age distribution, urbanization) and social trends (like increasing health consciousness, environmental awareness) can influence investment priorities.

Global Trends and Market Dynamics: Understanding how global trends (like digital transformation, sustainability, remote work) impact your country is important.

Once you provide more specific information, I can offer a tailored analysis of the priority directions for business and entrepreneurial investment in your country.

As of my last update in April 2023, I can't provide real-time or country-specific economic data, including the current priority directions for business and entrepreneurial investment in your country. However, I can outline general trends and sectors that were gaining attention globally as of early 2023. For the most current and specific information, I recommend consulting local economic reports, investment advisors, or governmental economic development agencies in your country.

Technology and Digitalization: Investment in tech startups and companies focusing on AI, machine learning, big data, and cybersecurity has been a global trend. The digital transformation of traditional businesses is also a key area.

Sustainable and Renewable Energy: With a growing focus on combating climate change, renewable energy sources like solar, wind, and bioenergy are attracting significant investments.

Healthcare and Biotechnology: The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the importance of healthcare innovation. Biotech, telemedicine, and personalized medicine are areas with high potential.

E-Commerce and Online Services: The shift towards online shopping and digital services is expected to continue, making this a lucrative investment area.

Food and Agriculture Technology: With a growing global population, innovative solutions in food production, agricultural technology, and sustainable practices are increasingly important.

Education Technology (EdTech): The demand for online learning and educational technologies is growing, making this a promising investment area.

FinTech: Financial technology, especially in mobile banking, payments, and blockchain, is transforming the financial sector and is a key investment area.

Infrastructure and Real Estate Development: Especially in emerging markets, investing in infrastructure and real estate can be a priority, including smart city projects and sustainable urban development.

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Initiatives: Investments that focus on sustainability and social responsibility are gaining traction.

Manufacturing and Supply Chain Innovation: With global supply chain disruptions, investments in supply chain resilience and advanced manufacturing technologies are becoming more important.

Entertainment and Media: The growth in streaming services, gaming, and online content creation presents opportunities for investment.

CONCLUSION

Remember, the suitability of these sectors for investment can vary significantly based on your country's economic context, regulatory environment, and market maturity. It's always important to conduct thorough research or consult with a local expert before making investment decisions.

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